

Emerging need for Introducing courses B.H.Ed., and M.H.Ed., to the College and University Teachers

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Received: February 04, 2016| Revised: February 20, 2016| Accepted: February 27, 2016

Published online: March 07, 2016

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Abstract: India is undergoing paradigm shift in Higher Education in an incredible proportion. Time has come for review of our system of education at higher level in the wake of quality aspects which are largely criticized by the competent boards and authorities. It is predominantly essential to give a strong foundation to the Teachers at various levels irrespective of the discipline. This article is aimed at introducing Teacher Training courses at tertiary education level to produce the skilled educators for inculcating higher education with a logical system and meaningful order. The need for quality faculty in the maintenance of educational standards need not be overemphasized.

1. INTRODUCTION

“As long as the trunk is firm, don’t worry about the branches swaying with the wind”, which tells us the need for strong foundation in any sort of profession. In the system of education it is essential to give a strong foundation to the clients at various levels. No doubt the strong foundation comes out from the sound educational practice and intensive training. A deep study of any work or problem warrants a thorough analysis of the basics so that it can withstand any criticism of others. Such homework will throw up answers to problems and ways to implement any programme. This sane principle applies more so educational problems. Teaching profession is a significant causative factor to bring in effective changes in the society. Shri- Narendra Modi, Hon’ble Prime Minister of India has pointed out that “Education should become a force for the nation’s character building”, Further he has stated that “If our teacher is

Issues and Ideas
in Education
Vol- 4, No- 1
March 2016
pp. 63–70

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not a few steps ahead of time, the society will not be ahead". Her Excellency Pratibha Devisingh Patil, the former President of India while delivering the Convocation address at the 25th Convocation of Ranchi University, Jharkhand on 10th December 2010 has mentioned that "Nations with high quality human resources would be counted amongst the front ranking nations of the world in the knowledge era. Therefore, we have to be careful that by concentrating on quantity we do not compromise on quality. Quality faculty is important to maintain high standards of our universities, so that world class graduates, postgraduates and doctoral students are produced. There is also the need for the faculty to equip themselves with the required knowledge and technical skills to cater to the demand of the global markets. There is also an express need to upgrade the curricula, to equip classrooms, laboratories and libraries" (Excerpts). When the system of education is formalized without any flaw at various levels, the quality can easily be attained and definitely it leads to excellence in all the fields of knowledge.

2. NATIONAL MISSION FOR TEACHERS TRAINING

Pandit Madan Mohan Malviya National Mission on Teachers and Teaching (PMMMNMTT) was launched on 25th December 2014 by the Ministry of Human Resource Development in honour of the Great Savant. The Government of India is mandated to launch PMMMNMTT with the following goals:

Goal – 1: To ensure a coordinated approach so as to holistically address the various shortcomings relating to teachers and teaching across the educational spectrum ranging from school education to higher education including technical education; using the best international practices for excellence.

As per this first goal the education system must address holistically the various shortcomings relating to teachers and teaching across the educational spectrum. Therefore, it is necessary to have teacher training courses for the teachers who are employed and to be employed in tertiary education. Introduction of courses for College and University teachers who are facilitating tertiary education to the adolescents after obtaining post-graduation will largely benefit and acquire the competencies of teaching skills by the training courses of Bachelor of Higher Education (B. H. Ed.) and Master of Higher Education (M. H. Ed.). The existing system of education has been made mandatory for the school teachers to obtain D. T. Ed., B.Ed., and M.Ed., for transacting school curriculum; the tertiary education system also need to be systematized with the pedagogy training courses. By introducing these courses, our country would be the first country to ensure the system of education in perfect order.

Goal – 2: To create and strengthen the institutional mechanisms (Schools of Education, Institutes of Academic leadership and Education Management, Subject based networks, Teaching–learning Centres etc.) at the Centre & in the States, for augmenting training and discipline–wise capacity building of faculty and their periodic assessment for excellence.

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In response to this goal, Introduction of Teacher training courses at tertiary level would ensure the strengthening of educational system and facilitate the tertiary education faculties to enhance their capacity as well as teaching skills. Establishing College and University Teacher training centres at the Central and State Universities would easily bring the paradigm shift in the tertiary education system.

Goal – 3: To empower teachers and faculty through training, re-training, refresher and orientation programmes in generic skills, pedagogic skills, discipline specific content up-gradation, ICT and technology enabled training and other appropriate interventions.

With regard to the third goal, the tertiary education faculties before entering into the profession must possess entry qualification as basic Teacher Training, competencies of facilitating learning, perspectives in education, ICT enabled and technology friendly training and acquiring mastery of specific enriched content skills are easily accessed by the Teacher trainee through these B. H. Ed and M. H. Ed courses.

The following mission statements are made by the MHRD by transforming the above goals of PMMMNMTT:

Mission – I: The Teacher training will address all issues related to teachers, teaching, teacher preparation, professional development, curriculum design.

Mission – II: An umbrella scheme which will create synergies among the various ongoing initiatives on Teachers and Teaching.

Mission – III: Develop a strong professional cadre of teachers by setting performance standards and creating top class institutional facilities for innovative teaching.

Mission – IV: Address the need to induct qualified teachers, attracting talent into teaching profession and raising the quality of teaching in schools and colleges.

In order to give practical shape to the quality education; the proposed courses will definitely bring expected changes in the system of education as a whole.

3. NEED AND IMPORTANCE OF INTRODUCING B.H.ED., AND M.H.ED., COURSES

Introduction of Bachelor of Higher Education (B.H.Ed.) and Master of Higher Education (M.H.Ed.) is indeed a must to maintain high standard in Tertiary

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Education. In higher education, the high standard can be attained only through quality faculty. The system of education which is prevailing in our country fails to produce quality faculty at tertiary level because of vacuum in introducing training and teaching degree at higher level. At higher level, faculties strive to facilitate the students initially at the time of starting of the career; however, the faculty develops the ability to deliver up to the expectations only after acquiring 10 to 15 years of teaching experience. Initially, they want to equip themselves with respect to the subject dealt in the classroom. The efficiency of instruction will depend on the sophisticated and well tried teaching methods through the application of advanced technology and gadgets. With the judicious use of teaching methods, a teacher should make his instruction sprightly with his mastery of the art of class management. He should win the hearts and minds of his pupils, here his clients to whom he owes ultimate allegiance. His skills are at full display. He understands their psychology and panders to their needs in a sympathetic manner. His lessons with meaningful concepts implicit philosophy, sacred values are delight to their minds. The modern educational technology, evaluation procedures and his scientifically prepared question papers — all these come handy to strengthen his teaching and deliver fruits. The faculty becomes what he does. All these aspects play a very significant role to become quality faculty. There are ample examples we can come across in tertiary level education that the faculties with maximum percentage of marks in the core subjects fail to deliver the good to the students because of lack of knowledge and practice in teaching methodology and there are certain faculties with moderate percentage of marks in the main subjects do the other way round by equipping fully well the pertinent teaching competencies. No doubt, the empirical knowledge definitely contributes in any profession but we cannot wait till then. Therefore, there is a need for introducing these courses for the cause of enhancing the quality of higher education and betterment of the society.

4. PREVAILING CONDITIONS

As per the socially accepted norms, a person with Postgraduate qualification with or without Master of Philosophy or Doctor of Philosophy or NET/SLET can enter into the profession of teaching at tertiary level. M.Phil and Ph.D in respective field will give advancement of knowledge in the chosen subject and may not enhance the methodology of teaching. Research degrees are meant for bringing out new ideas of particular knowledge in specific subject; which means in research nothing is wrong and nothing is right; it is a view point. But the degree of acceptance and the utility differ from subject to subject and discipline to discipline. The prevailing condition is such that a person is qualified to become

a faculty in Colleges and Universities by obtaining Postgraduate degree with or without research degree and NET qualification, but doesn't qualify to teach at Primary, Secondary and Higher Secondary levels because of not possessing the Teaching diploma or degree. It is shocking, when it is seen that after Higher Secondary Education a person gets himself trained in Secondary Grade Training and remains unemployed and to exhaust his excess time in hand goes up further and further up to Doctorate, the unemployment factor haunting him throughout. If at all that overqualified trained person gets appointed at primary or middle levels and continues with no Bachelor of Education (B.Ed) degree and when promotional prospects open up for others stands denied to him for the lack of Bachelor degree in education. At one side, the system of education says that a person is qualified for handling classes at Higher Education but on the other side not qualified to handle at lower level. So, there exists an anomaly in the system of education. If teaching diploma or degree is a must to become a teacher as per the prevailing conditions at school levels then why not at the tertiary level also which is becoming increasingly important to determine the fate of the country. Largely, Graduates and Postgraduates of all disciplines are starting their professional, social, economical and political life only after obtaining higher education.

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5. QUALIFICATION CRITERIA FOR TERTIARY LEVEL TEACHER EDUCATION

The Bachelor of Higher Education and Master of Higher Education should be made mandatory to become the faculty at tertiary level education. The tertiary level may be of Arts, Science, Humanities, Social Science, Law, Engineering and Technology and or Medicine. Irrespective of any discipline, the course should be made compulsory. The NET/SLET should serve only for filtration or to minimize the competition or to award fellowship but not to be fixed as qualification to become a teacher at higher level. By mere getting through the NET/SLET one cannot acquire the art and science of teaching skills at tertiary level. Research is not everybody's fare, Master of Philosophy and Doctor of Philosophy must be awarded only to the deserving research scholars and should not be kept as an entry qualification for the teaching profession at higher level. At the same time such higher qualification should not be diluted largely by keeping research degree as minimum requirement for the teaching career at higher level. Those who are obtaining research degree after becoming a faculty in higher educational institutions may be considered for higher promotion with suitable increments and incentives. So, it is necessary to be considered by the learned society that the research degrees are meant for furtherance of chosen field of knowledge and not for the determining of earning the teaching profession. Thenceforth, introducing of B.H.Ed., and M.H.Ed., becomes inevitable.

Qualification for the various levels of education

Qualifications

Teaching Positions

Course Structure

The following curriculum structure is proposed for the Bachelor of Higher Education (B. H. Ed) course.

Course Description

Theory:

1. Language – English
2. Core Course:
 - i) Basics in Education
 - ii) Curriculum and College Instruction
 - iii) Psychology of Learning and Teaching
3. Optional Subjects: Two Pedagogical subjects chosen on the basis of their major subjects studied at undergraduate level.

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4. Elective Subjects: One subject must be chosen out of four elective subjects.

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Practicum:

5. Important components for obtaining training which comprises of both Work based practicum and College based practicum.

The curriculum structure for the Master of Higher Education (M. H. Ed) course is designed to enhance the educands capability to handle at postgraduate level. The M. H. Ed., course is to enhance the skills of Teachers to be useful to pupil through indirectly to reinforce their dedication and outlook to the education and teaching profession with particular reference to senior adolescents and adults. Curriculum for the M. H. Ed., can be designed in accordance with the respective discipline post-graduation courses.

Modalities of the courses

Initially, the courses should be offered to the working faculty and must be conducted only by the Universities which have the concerned discipline with proper infrastructure. Faculties who are going to handle the courses should be handpicked from all over the India who excels in the particular discipline and having at least 20 years of experience in the teaching profession at higher level with Doctoral degree preferably Post Doctoral degree. Primarily, senior faculties from the school of education possibly retired professors' help may be sought out for the conducting of the programme feasibly along with the respective discipline of chosen faculties.

There will be peevishness at the initial stage but once it comes to formalization, the society will accept the change. The change is only for the cause of quality higher education and not for the sake of adding either courses or burdens. B.H.Ed., degree is mandatory for the existing faculties of any discipline as well as aspiring faculties to handle all the Bachelor degrees and M.H.Ed., degree should be made mandatory for the existing faculties as well as aspiring faculties to handle all Master degrees in respect of all disciplines.

Since, they are undergoing 5 years duration for completing Post graduation in Arts, Science, Humanities, Social Sciences and Law, Bachelor degree in Engineering, Technology and 8 years duration in Medicine; the course duration for both B.H.Ed., and M.H.Ed., for them should be fixed as one year each. For the existing working faculties the courses may be designed for two consecutive year's duration as summer sequential programme to avoid conflict in conducting regular courses. The minimum requirement to join B.H.Ed., is a Master degree or equivalent degree in any discipline and to join M.H.Ed., a Master degree with B.H.Ed.,

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Objectives of introducing these courses: The following objectives are framed for introducing of B.H.Ed., and M.H.Ed., courses:

1. To bring tertiary education educands in the system of Teacher Education.
2. To enhance the teaching efficiency of tertiary education educands.
3. To prepare the tertiary education educands with professional preservice training.
4. To maintain highest standards of excellence in Higher Education.
5. To promote permanent assets (Higher Education Teachers) to the society.

Governing Authority

The said courses should be conducted by only the Central and State Universities by creating a separate department with the concurrence of competent authority. Here, the role of NCTE should be enhanced to govern and smoothen the conducting of these courses. The universities should be given complete autonomy in terms of conducting the courses like other courses. Initially, periodical assessment should be done at least for five years and rest of the procedures should be as usual. There shouldn't be any problem in recognizing the courses throughout the country and the UGC should give direction to all the State Governments and the Universities which conduct the courses. Criteria for admission procedure and evaluation etc should be framed uniformly throughout the country by the competent authorities while sitting across the table in the interest of maintaining proper standards in higher education.

CONCLUSION

There will be always resistance from various corners for the new initiation in educational arena but considering the significance of the courses and in order to bring the entire educational system in systemic and systematic order, it is inevitable to introduce these courses without fail by giving priority. Thinking well is wise; Planning well is wiser; Doing well is the wisest and the best of all.

REFERENCES

- [1] University News, A Weekly Journal of Higher Education, **49(4)**, January 2011.
- [2] 200 days new vision, new approach e-view, MHRD.
- [3] PMMMNMTT Guidelines, Department of Higher Education, MHRD, Govt. of India, May, 2015.